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Lived- Experiences on Resiliency of Economically Disadvantaged Students in Face-To-Face Learning

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Abstract

This study focused on the lived experiences of resiliency of economically disadvantaged students in face-to-face learning. Economically disadvantaged students faced different challenges to be resilient in learning, on how their day to day learning activities can survive due to financial difficulties to support their everyday needs. This phenomenon was considered since it had an impact on students' learning performance. The study was anchored on theories on Resilience Theory as popularized by Tellegen (2012) and Self-Determination Theory by Deci and Ryan (2008). This study employed a qualitative research method: namely, a transcendental method of research to explore and understand the lived experiences of resiliency of economically disadvantaged students in their learning, as well as their challenges and practices to continue in their learning, acquiring data from 10 participants in Barangay Bagnoy, San Juan, Aliaga, Nueva Ecija. The participants were chosen using purposive sampling technique wherein thematic analysis was used to analyze all the gathered data. The findings revealed that socio-economic status impacted economically disadvantaged students' educational experiences. The study generated five (5) themes, categories and codes. This study found out that being economically disadvantaged students do not prevent them to employ various strategies in learning towards improvement of their academic performance. It was also found out that classmates and friends, family and teachers were all the factors that contributed to students' resiliency and academic success. And to overcome academic challenges, economically disadvantaged students used coping strategies such as good study habits, time management, financial planning, and high sense of self-determination.

Keywords: *economically disadvantaged students, face-to-face learning, lived-experiences, resiliency*

Introduction

Economically disadvantaged students have hindrances to excelling in school because of the financial problems within their families to support their learning needs. Sometimes, they cannot attend class regularly because of a lack of money to pay for transportation. They need to walk for an hour just to go to school. Some have no allowance to buy their food and other learning materials. Being an economically disadvantaged student, it is very difficult to continue learning and have an impact on their academic achievements. Based on studies, economically disadvantaged students go to school with insufficient funding or resources that affect their academic achievements and an inability to provide for their everyday needs, which can cause them to drop out (Bradley, 2022). However, economically disadvantaged students were resilient enough to continue learning.

Despite being economically disadvantaged learners, they needed to be more resilient to continue in learning. Resilient learners always find ways to ease their frustration and focus on learning. They had the ability to bounce back from challenges by studying harder despite experiences of financial difficulties. They attended their class regularly even though they had no allowance for their snacks. They went to school by walking for almost 30 minutes to an hour because of a lack of money to pay for services or transportation, and they had limited learning materials to use in learning. But still, they continue to learn based on what they have and show their resiliency to overcome all challenges as economically disadvantaged learners.

By this, resiliency is one of the most essential tools that help them manage these experiences, recover from them, and thrive afterward. So, being resilient is the key to building our happiness and well-being toward educational progress, specifically in face-to-face learning. Based on the researcher's experiences in teaching, many students have difficulties procuring their learning materials to comply with the learning competencies needed to accomplish as part of their academic achievements. Some could not attend classes because they lacked money to support their daily allowances and educational needs. Hence, academically resilient students are those who, despite being economically disadvantaged, have the ability to overcome the obstacles in their way and maintain their good academic standing. Economically disadvantaged students often have low-educated parents who work in lower-paid and less-prestigious jobs. These are among the reasons why students are often deprived of their needs regarding educational and resource materials at home (Roffey, 2019).

Thus, resiliency has gained more importance as a skill for students to develop and face their challenges and difficulties in learning. Because resiliency deeply embedded sources and guides mental barriers to students' learning. Academic resilience could be the functional interface of education policies of "education for everyone" and "education is free from all" that would contribute to the learning and resiliency of the students with economically disadvantaged. Thus, resilient learners are able to move forward after a difficult breakup and overcome stress or traumatic events in their lives, just like how economically disadvantaged students face their challenging lives and continue learning despite their situations.

This qualitative study aimed to explore and understand the lived experiences of economically disadvantaged students in face-to-face learning in the Barrio of Nueva Ecija. It also explores their challenges in learning, especially face-to-face setups, and how the

participants continued to perform their tasks despite their economic conditions as students.

A practical knowledge gap tends to be a discrepancy that can motivate new research in this direction. A practical–knowledge (action-knowledge) conflict arises when the actual behavior of professionals is different from their advocated behavior. Research in this instance could aim to ascertain the extent of the dispute and identify the causes of it (Müller-Bloch & Kranz, 2014). This is due to a possible misalignment between the strategies or interventions that are recommended for promoting resilience among economically disadvantaged students and the actual practices that are put into practice in face-to-face learning environments. This could show up as differences between the best practices that are advised to be used in order to serve these pupils and the difficulties that teachers and school administrators face on a daily basis. Research can help develop more practical and effective ways to support economically disadvantaged students in face-to-face learning environments by defining the extent of this conflict and revealing the underlying causes of it.

Research Questions

This transcendental phenomenological study was to explore the lived experiences of the resiliency of economically disadvantaged students in face-to-face learning in the Barrio of Nueva Ecija. This study explored how economically disadvantaged students are resilient to continue in learning. How their difficulties are overcome despite their financial difficulties to provide their learning needs in day-to-day activities on going to school. How resilient they were to still study harder to perform well in their study and to withstand their difficulties in learning. What are the ways individuals view and engage in learning, how do they have available learning resources, and what are their specific coping mechanisms to address their challenges?

According to the American Psychological Association (2020), resilience is the process and outcome of successfully adapting to difficult or challenging experiences, especially through mental, emotional and behavioral flexibility and adjustment to external and internal demands. The study used a transcendental phenomenological research design; the resilience will be used to connect on how the lived experiences of economically disadvantaged students residing in the Barrio of Nueva Ecija will be described in this study. In this study, resilience is the ability of a person to adapt and overcome difficult times at hand (Amelasih, 2019); more so, the ability to adapt from risks, difficulties, and some monumental adverse events constructively and positively. In an era characterized by the commitment to leave no student behind, this research seeks to unravel the essence of resiliency, recognizing its pivotal role in overcoming challenges as economically disadvantaged students face in face-to-face learning. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the descriptions of economically disadvantaged students who live in a barrio in Nueva Ecija that pertain to academic resilience?
2. How do economically disadvantaged students who live in a barrio in Nueva Ecija stay resilient to improve their academic performance?
3. How do these economically disadvantaged students, influenced by their parents, and teachers, stay resilient in facing all challenges in life as a student?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used a qualitative transcendental phenomenological research design to answer the problem statements of this study on the lived experiences on resiliency of economically disadvantaged students in face-to-face learning. This transcendental phenomenological research was used in this study to explore the lived experiences of resilient of economically disadvantaged students in everyday challenges in face-to-face learning. Transcendental phenomenological research was deemed to be the most fitting approach in this context, as it is intended to thoroughly investigate the very core of the phenomenon being examined - its complexities, expressions, and diverse viewpoints that have contributed to shaping it. Transcendental phenomenological research was tagged as "the study of the nature of phenomena," including "their quality, different manifestations, the context in which they appear or the perspectives from which they can be perceived," but excluding "their range, frequency, and place in an objectively determined chain of cause and effect" (Busetto, Wick & Gumbinger, 2020).

Specifically, qualitative research utilized transcendental phenomenology to explore the life experiences and resiliency of economically disadvantaged students. A transcendental phenomenological approach used narrative for interviews, personal accounts/narratives (single event or episode) and lived experience. This allowed the researcher to engage in flexible activities that can describe and help to understand complex phenomena such as various aspects of human social experience. (Creswell, 2013).

Transcendental phenomenology, was largely developed by Husserl, is a philosophical approach to qualitative research methodology seeking to understand human experience. It creates more value and richness in the study of human experiences and elements that affect individuals in decision-making. It will seek a deeper understanding of the meaning of everyday experiences and ask "What is this experience like? And "How did individuals experience this phenomena, (Sheehan, 2018).

Participants

In this phenomenological study, the computed Age Dependency Ratios mean that among the population of San Juan, there are 45 youth dependents to every 100 of the working age population. Therefore there were 52 dependents (young and old-age) to every 100 of the working population (PhilAtlas, 2020). The selection process for the 10 student participants was based on a set of rigorous criteria. Firstly, the participants were required that he/she must be currently enrolled as grade 10 students at San Juan Integrated Schools, as this would enable them to provide a well-informed account of their experiences as economically disadvantaged students. Secondly, the selection criteria stipulated that the parents of the participants must have a monthly income below Php 10,000. Thirdly, no additional source of income other than their main job and no other form of support from relatives. Fourthly, the selection process also took into consideration the distance of the participant's residence from the school. Fifthly, limited or non-existent allowance, and lastly, the willingness of the participant to actively and meaningfully participate in the study.

Instruments

The researcher used three different methods in gathering needed data in accordance to achieve the objectives of the study such as interview, observation, and documents.

Interview. A semi-structured interview was used to gather the needed data and this is known as hybrid interview. A semi-structured interview is a qualitative research method that combines a predetermined set of open questions with the opportunity for the interviewer to explore particular themes or responses further (Barclay, 2018).

In this semi-structured interview, the researcher and participants engaged in a formal interview, then the researcher developed and used an interview guide. Also, the open ended nature of the questions defined the topic under investigation but provided opportunities for both researcher and the participants to discuss some topics in more detail. And lastly, the researcher followed the interview guide, but was able to follow relevant lines of enquiry in the conversation that may stray from the guide when they feel this is appropriate.

Observation. The researcher used informal observation to get additional data that supports the needed data on the lived experiences of resiliency of economically disadvantaged students in the Barrio of Nueva Ecija. The researcher used informal observation to triangulate data obtained through interview. She observed how the lived experiences and resiliency of the students at school such as their time going to class, their behavior in learning and how they are resourceful to sustain their learning needs.

Observation enabled the researcher to observe, interact and gain a rich picture of participants in their natural environment. This data collection method allowed the researcher to better understand the processes, culture or people under study (Delve, 2021).

Documentation. In this qualitative phenomenological research, the utilization of pictorial documentation can prove to be a potent technique for capturing and comprehending the lived experiences of participants. Documentation was beneficial in such a way that when the participants' verbal expressions alone were unable to adequately convey the intricacies and profundity of such experiences. In this study, it is done through inviting the participants and allowing them to contribute pictures that they perceive that have connections to the aspect of their lived experiences related to the phenomenon that was being studied. Lastly, this participatory approach empowered the participants and ensured that the pictures are meaningful and relevant to them.

Procedure

During the collection phase of actual data, several procedures were followed to ensure ethical and accurate data gathering. Firstly, the researcher obtained permission and approval from the parents of the participants through a consent letter. Once the approval has been granted, two informed consent forms were prepared and signed, with one copy given to the participant and the other retained by the researcher for documentation purposes. Eligible participants were then selected based on the inclusion criteria and in-depth interviews were conducted by the researcher to explore the lived experiences of resiliency of economically disadvantaged students. The researcher introduced herself and explained the purpose, objective, and significance of the study to the participant before commencing the interview.

The in-depth interviews were conducted face-to-face and the researcher used a mobile phone and recorded audio during the interview to ensure the accuracy and completeness of the data. Each interview was expected to last for approximately 30 minutes, and ample time was given to the participants for them to provide concrete and honest answers. Additionally, daily learning activities of the participants was observed and recorded to validate and cross-examine their responses during the interview.

Finally, a debriefing session was conducted to allow each participant to verbalize their feelings regarding the interview. The researcher expressed her gratitude for the time provided and concluded the interview by asking a final question for clarification. The gathered data was then encoded, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted to arrive at meaningful conclusions. These procedures ensure that ethical and accurate data was collected, that can then be used to advance the understanding of resiliency among economically disadvantaged students.

Data Analysis

All data gathered were encoded, recorded, analyzed and interpreted using themes and coding and extensively interpreted based on the responses of the participants. Since this is qualitative research, the researcher used content and narrative analysis based on the participants responses on the open-ended questions.

For the content analysis, the researcher used the Transcendental Framework analysis of Moustakas (1994), extracting codes from the responses, categorizing them, and finally identifying themes through careful analysis, interpretation, and contextualization. The method used helped transform qualitative input to help the researcher to make reliable conclusions about the life experiences of economically disadvantaged students. And then, from the data gathered the researcher conducted a content analysis manually to reveal patterns, themes or codes and analyzed based on themes and sub-themes.

And with regards to narrative analysis, the research utilized this method to interpret the participants' stories with valuable insight into the complexity of their testimonies, lives, feelings and behaviors as economically disadvantaged students. Hence, this method provides the researcher a deep understanding of the live experiences of economically disadvantaged students in face-to-face learning to formulate conclusions on the participants. The framework of Moustakas has eight different steps in analyzing the data namely, horizontalization, reduction and elimination clustering and thematizing, validation, individual textual description, individual structural description textural-structural description and essence.

Horizontalization

In this process the researcher listed and grouped all the significant responses from the participants through reading and rereading the verbatim transcription (Buenacosa & Patella, 2022). This allowed the researcher to have an equitable processing of all the input while recording all relevant information, including words, phrases, sentences, and emotional reactions. The researcher encoded her prior understanding of the themes in this approach.

Reduction and Elimination

In this process, the researcher determined the invariant constituents by reducing and removing irrelevant data. She criticized and analyzed well all data relevant to the lived-experiences of resiliency of economically disadvantaged students. All data not significant and relevant to the study was removed or excluded, only relevant data to the phenomenon was retained and used in study.

Clustering and Thematizing

In this process, all data gathered was categorized into clusters to form themes and sub-themes. It involved coding of a qualitative data set and used codes as cluster or theme variables. With this method, it helped the researcher to identify themes, patterns in the data that are relevant to the research inappropriate to the phenomena of the study.

Validation

Throughout this process, the researcher asked whether the tool—specifically, the interview guide question—was in line with the study's objectives. To find out if the interview guide question matched the research objectives, the researcher scheduled a meeting with the adviser and after the consultation, the researcher made necessary arrangements as per the instructions of the researcher's adviser.

Individual Textual Description

In this process, the researcher crafted the individual textual descriptions of each participant by incorporating relevant and appropriate elements that remained consistent throughout the data gathering procedure, including themes and the exact, word-for-word excerpts from the transcriptions.

Individual Structural Description

In this process, each participant has their own structural description on their lived experiences and resiliency as economically disadvantaged students based on the phenomena. In this situation, careful understanding and analysis was required to have a better analysis and interpretations of the data.

Textural-Structural Description

This process is also known as a Synthesis. This process the researcher began to combine textual and structural data to provide in depth analysis and interpretation on the phenomena to create themes and sub-themes that best described the lived-experience of resiliency of economically disadvantaged students.

Essence

From the structural and textual descriptions, the researcher then writes a composite description that presents the essence of the phenomenon. Primarily this passages focuses on the common experiences of the participants of the study.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations play a vital role in any research study. These include voluntary participation of the participants, informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, the potential for harm, and the privacy of results and communication. Research ethical considerations are a set of principles that guide researchers' research designs and practices. It must always adhere to a certain code of conduct when collecting data from the participants/respondents. Its goals often include understanding real-life phenomena, studying

effective treatment, investigating behaviors and improving lives in other ways. The ethical considerations plays an important role in research to protect the rights of research participants, enhance research validity, and maintain scientific and academic integrity (Bhandari, 2023).

The participants were informed about the voluntary nature of their participation and were given the freedom to leave the study at any point in time, even if their parents had already signed the consent form. Before the commencement of the study, the participants were informed that a letter seeking permission to conduct the research had been submitted to the proper authorities, including the principal and school division superintendent.

To guarantee the credibility and consistency of the data collection process, the interview guide questions were meticulously scrutinized by the researcher's adviser before being administered to the participants. Once the participants had finished the face-to-face interview, their real identities were kept confidential, and only the pertinent information was selected for the study. The researcher also took all necessary precautions to ensure that the study did not cause any harm to the participants, whether it was physical, social, psychological, or emotional. Additionally, the results of this study were neither copied nor plagiarized. Moreover, the researcher was mindful of the potential for changes during the data collection process and the probability of intimate information being disclosed. To minimize any possible harm or discomfort, the researcher was especially cautious during the interview process, particularly since the participants were minors.. And to safeguard the privacy and security of the participants' data, the study was conducted under the Data Privacy Act of 2012. This act emphasizes the need to protect the fundamental human right of privacy and communication while promoting the free flow of information to encourage innovation and growth (Republic Act No. 10173, Ch.1, Sec.2; National Privacy Commission, 2012). The researcher ensured that all data and information, including names, contact numbers, addresses, and others, were kept strictly confidential and used solely for the study.

Lastly, the study strictly adhered to the ethical guidelines, ensuring that the participants' physical and mental well-being were not compromised in any way. The researcher had taken all necessary measures to maintain the confidentiality and privacy of the participants' data, thereby safeguarding their fundamental human rights.

Results and Discussion

Participants' Demographic Profile

The ten participants of this qualitative research are economically disadvantaged Grade 10 students from Barrio of Bagnoy, San Juan, Aliaga, Nueva Ecija. These young individuals faced financial challenges, with their parents earning less than 10,000 pesos monthly. They have limited allowance, sometimes none, and live far from their school. Despite financial challenges, their experiences were marked by resilience and determination as they were committed to overcoming challenges and continuing their education.

Table 1. Summary of Participants Demographic Profile

Pseudonyms	Age	Sex	Grade Level	Parent Occupation		Parent's income	No. of Siblings	Daily Allowance
				Mother	Father			
Allen	15	M	10	Vendor	None	5,000	2	40
Meymey	16	F	10	None	Carpenter	6,000	3	50
Via	14	F	10	Maid	None	5,000	2	30
Arkin	15	M	10	dishwasher	Palay dryer	6,000	4	40
Ysabelle	15	F	10	Laundrywoman	Garbage collector	5,000	2	30
Ivan	15	M	10	Maid	None	5,000	3	50
Nathan	14	M	10	Cook	Carpenter	6,000	3	40
Althea	15	F	10	Laundry woman	Vendor	8,000	4	40
Justine	16	M	10	Laundy woman	Farmer	8,000	3	50
Angela	15	F	10	Street sweeper	Palay dryer	7,000	2	50

Participant 1, Allen

Allen is a 15-year-old male student in Grade 10. He comes from a family where his mother works as a vendor. Their household income is limited, but Allen receives a daily allowance of 40 pesos for his transportation and meals. Despite financial constraints, Allen is dedicated to his studies and prioritizes education over other distractions. He acknowledges the challenges of financial limitations but remains resilient, helping his parents by selling goods to earn extra income for school expenses. Allen's mother supports his education and provides financial assistance and guidance. With his family's support, Allen remains determined to pursue his academic goals and realizes the importance of education in achieving his aspirations.

Participant 2, Meymey

Meymey, a 16-year-old student, comes from a household where her father works as a carpenter, earning a moderate income to support their family. She has two younger siblings and receives a daily allowance of 50 pesos. She uses 20 pesos for her transportation fee and the remaining lunch money. Meymey faces various challenges in her daily life, balancing her academic responsibilities with household

duties since she is the eldest. Despite financial constraints, Meymey demonstrates a solid commitment to her studies by diligently setting schedules for completing assignments and engaging in self-directed learning. She values her support network, which encourages and assists her to excel academically despite the challenges.

Participant 3, Via

Via is a 14-year-old female student from a family where her mother works as a maid. Their household income is limited to 5,000 pesos, and Via has two siblings. She faces challenges due to financial constraints, as her daily allowance of 30 pesos is insufficient to cover her daily school expenses. Despite these difficulties, she prioritizes saving her allowance for potential school projects and refrains from snacking to manage her finances better. Via actively listens in class and understands the importance of education regardless of financial limitations. When her allowance runs out, she occasionally borrows money from friends. Additionally, she struggles with the workload and seeks help from classmates to understand lessons and complete activities.

Participant 4, Arkin

Arkin, a 15-year-old boy in Grade 10, comes from a family where his mother works as a dishwasher in a restaurant and his father works as a rice paddy dryer, earning a monthly income of 7,000 pesos to support their four children. Despite financial constraints, Arkin shows resourcefulness and resilience in his academic journey. He often brings leftover food from home for lunch to save money, as his daily allowance is only 40 pesos. He also diligently studies at home to keep up with his classmates. Arkin relies on his aunt's support for his education, as his parents cannot provide full support due to their large family.

Participant 5, Ysabelle

Ysabelle, a 15-year-old female student, comes from a household where her mother works as a laundry woman and her father is a garbage collector, with a monthly income of 5,000 pesos supporting their family of four. Despite financial constraints, Ysabelle remains resilient and motivated by her dreams and family. She attends school even without a daily allowance, believing that poverty should not hinder the pursuit of dreams. Ysabelle diligently reviews her lessons at home and seeks help from teachers and family members when facing difficulties. She emphasizes the importance of positivity and appreciates the support and guidance provided by her teachers, who visit their homes to check on their well-being and offer advice. Ysabelle's determination and support system, including her teachers and family, contribute to her academic progress and belief in achieving her life goals despite the challenges posed by economic limitations.

Participant 6, Ivan

Ivan, a 15-year-old male student in Grade 10, comes from a family where his mother works as a maid, with no additional income from his father since the start of the pandemic. Their household income is limited, and Ivan receives a daily allowance of 50 pesos, which he barely manages because of the fare to enter the school due to the distance from their house. Despite facing financial constraints, Ivan demonstrates resilience and determination in his studies. He acknowledges the challenges of managing limited resources but emphasizes his efforts to stay on track by seeking help from classmates and dedicating time to studying regularly.

Participant 7, Nathan

Nathan, a 14-year-old male student in Grade 10, comes from a family where his mother works as a cook and his father is a carpenter. Their combined income is 6,000 pesos, supporting Nathan and his two siblings. Despite financial constraints and the challenges of managing household duties alongside schoolwork, Nathan demonstrates resilience and determination in his studies. He diligently saves his daily allowance for emergencies and utilizes his savings to ensure he can attend school even when there is no money for his allowance. He acknowledges the support of his family, especially his mother, and teachers, in providing encouragement and assistance when needed. Nathan emphasizes the importance of perseverance and resourcefulness in overcoming financial limitations to continue his education.

Participant 8, Althea

Althea, a 15-year-old female student in Grade 10, comes from a family where her mother works as a laundry woman, and her father is a vendor. Despite their modest income of 8,000 pesos and having four siblings, Althea manages to navigate her academic journey amidst financial and personal challenges. She believes that going to school, even without money for daily expenses, is acceptable as long as one is actively engaged in learning. Althea demonstrates resilience and resourcefulness by finding solutions to financial problems independently or seeking support from her family when necessary. Althea remains committed to her education, seeking help from teachers and family members when needed and seeing challenges as chances for growth and improvement. Despite her obstacles, Althea remains determined to excel academically and make her parents proud.

Participant 9, Justine

Justine, a 16-year-old male student, comes from a family where his mother works as a laundry woman, and his father is a farmer, providing a household income of 8,000 pesos to support their family. Justine receives a daily allowance of 50 pesos but needs more for all his daily expenses in school. He faces financial challenges, often receiving insufficient allowance and needing to prioritize expenses.

Despite these hardships, Justine is dedicated to his studies, seeking help from classmates and devoting time to reading and listening to his teachers. He remains optimistic and strives to understand his lessons, motivated by his parents' support and encouragement.

Participant 10, Angela

Angela, a 15-year-old seventh-grade student, faces the challenges of her studies with determination and resourcefulness despite financial constraints. Her parents work as a street sweeper and a palay dryer, providing a modest income of 7,000 pesos for their family of four. Angela receives a daily allowance of 50 pesos, which she manages through frugal spending and sacrifices like skipping morning recess to save money for transportation. She utilizes vacant periods and weekends to review her lessons and complete assignments, demonstrating proactive learning habits. She believes her determination to succeed in school is for herself and alleviating her family's poverty.

Theme 1: Academic Resilience Amid Socioeconomic Challenges

In the study, it was evident that poverty was one of the primary indicators of early adversity children encounter in the face-to-face learning environment. In this study, it found out that throughout the students' lived experiences during face-to-face learning, students navigate and overcome barriers related to economic disadvantage and social inequality in their studies. Economically disadvantaged students can still perform academic resilience and success in education despite the difficulties of their current situations.

Four categories arise from this theme, including financial challenges, academic struggles, stress and mental health, and resilience and overcoming challenges. In category 1: Financial Challenges, the economic constraints experienced by the participants reflected a broader socioeconomic disparities within their community. Limited parental income below the poverty line restricts access to necessities and educational resources. All participants faced various financial challenges that hinder academic success.

For instance, Participant 1, Allen, "Ang isa sa karanasan ko ay kinukulang ako minsan sa pinansyal." L9, in addition, Participant 3, Via "Maayos naman po, pero madalas po mahirap kasi po may kakulangan ako sa financial" L6, also Participant 10 Angela, "Minsan mahirap dahil sa kakulangan sa budget kapag may kailangan gastusin sa paaralan" L7-L8. Similarly, Participant 6 Ivan, "Mahirap dahil minsan ay hindi sapat ang naibibigay na baon at maraming bayarin ang kailangan unahin." L6 and Participant 7 Nathan, "Mahirap po minsan lalo kapag wala po kaming naibabaon" L6-L7.

Students have insufficient allowance for daily expenses and struggled to afford school supplies, projects, transportation, and even meals. It is evident in the responses of the student participants.

Participant 1, Allen "Mindan kahit anong tipid ay kinakapos pa rin talaga" L5, Participant 7 Nathan "Sobrang hirap po talaga mag-aral kapag walang pangkain at pamasaha" L13, L14, and Participant 10 Angela, "Minsan mahirap dahil sa kakulangan sa budget kapag may kailangan gastusin sa paaralan" L7-L8.

There was a study that indicated that financial constraints posed a significant challenge, as students struggled to immediately access necessary educational resources, particularly in data connectivity expenses. (Cleofe et al.,2022) The burden of financial strain weighs heavily on these young learners, often forcing them to prioritize essential needs over educational expenses.

The participants faced not only financial challenges but also academic struggles. In Category 2, Academic Struggles, challenges include problems with modern study strategies and were evident in some of the responses of the participants.

Participant 1 Allen stated "Ayos Naman Ang aking pag aaral ,mahirap din talaga ang pag aaral dahil sa makabagong stratehiya, may mga pagkakataon po na wala po akong load at mayron po kailangan pong i-search na mga assignments po na bigay ng teacher, hindi ko po magawa, L6-L10,

A participant also emphasized the difficulty understanding lessons and complex subjects.

Participant 9 Justine, "Nahihirapan ako minsan intindihin ang lesson hindi pumasok sa isip ko ang tinuturo ng teacher" L27-L28.

Also a study discussed that disadvantaged students demonstrate an impressive ability to attain satisfactory academic achievement and social adaptation despite their challenges (Mostafa, Gambaro, and Joshi, 2018). In addition, Baloyo and Trillanes (2023), stated that the factors influencing students' learning experiences included issues with internet connectivity, adjustments to new learning modalities, and financial constraints. Moreover, lack of access to technology for research and study purposes was also mentioned as barrier to academic progress.

Participant 6 Ivan, Nahihirapan po ako dahil pag kailangan pong isearch o may isesend ang teacher wala pong internet wala rin pong pang load dahil nga po hindi sapat yung pera. L15-L17.

Being overwhelmed by the volume of coursework was another challenge that was evident in the responses of the participants.

Participant 5 Ysabelle, stated the "Nahihirapan Po ako sa ibang pong activities" L23, Participant 10 Angela, "Ang mga balakid na aking nararanasan sa aking pag aaral ay ang pag sunod sunod ng mga gawain sa paaralan" L34- L35.

Category 3: Stress and Mental Health, the stress and mental health implications of financial strain and academic difficulties were

evident in the responses. Participants are overwhelmed due to the financial burden, academic workload, and personal responsibilities. It poses mental health problems to students struggling with their daily learning experiences. As a result, they are experiencing fatigue, stress, lack of motivation, and even moments of despair, which was affecting their overall mental health

Participant 7, Nathan, “Nakakastress po minsan pero okay naman at kaya naman.” L29, also, Participant 10 Angela, “nakakapagod at stress pero sulit naman lahat ng iyon dahil natututo din naman ako kahit papaano.” L6 .

The resilience of socioeconomically disadvantaged students has been linked to various dimensions encompassing educational, psychological, social, and personal characteristics (Özden & Atasoy, 2020). In line with this, Dwiastuti et al. (2022) found in a study that there was a significant positive correlation between academic resilience capacity and academic performance.

Lastly, in Category 4, Resilience and Overcoming Challenges, despite the challenges they faced, the respondent demonstrated resilience in various ways. They used different strategies, such as budgeting their allowance instead of giving up, these students have a resilient spirit.

For instance, Participant 2, Meymey, mentioned that “Nagagawa kong makipagsabayan sa pamamagitan ng pag aaral nang mabuti, L20 tuwing may load ang kaibigan ko ay nakikikonek ako upang maka download ng mga video tungkol sa pinag aaralan namin.” L23, also Participant 9, Angela, “pagkakaroon ng matatag at determinadong kaisipan” L51, also Participant 8, Althea, stated “There was a time na pumasok ako without having something to eat or money to buy some foods pero hindi yon nagging epekto para hindi ako pumasok” L10-L11 “isa lang ang ginagawa ko kayanin ang mga pagsubok mapa pinansyal o pansariling problema man yan.” L46-L47.

This study found that throughout the students' lived experiences during face-to-face learning, students navigated and overcome barriers related to economic disadvantages and social inequality in their studies.

As mentioned by Participant 4 Arkin, mentioned that “Hindi agad ako sumusuko sa pag-aaral kahit mahirap at maraming problema, dahil wala namang problema na hindi nasosolusyunan” L22-L23.

However, students must swiftly adapt to unexpected learning changes to attain their academic goals (Dhawan, 2020). They recognized that education was a crucial part of their future success and were committed to doing whatever it took to achieve their dreams. Their ability to push through difficult times showcases their natural strength and resourcefulness. Instead of giving up, these students have a resilient spirit. They see obstacles as opportunities for personal growth and development.

Thus, the more excellent academic resilience, the higher levels of academic achievement among students. Data from the observations revealed that participants do lack a lot of things, the Researcher observed that many of them were not taking any snacks just to save money for other school purposes, and as being indicated on the documentation, it can be seen that their houses are not built properly due to lack of finances.

Theme 2: Coping Strategies for Academic Achievement

Economically disadvantaged students use different coping strategies to improve their academics. They engage in a range of coping mechanisms, including problem-focused strategies such as financial planning, time management, and seeking academic support, as well as emotion-focused strategies like positive thinking and determination. These students develop different study habits and are committed to their academic success.

Three categories arise from this theme, study habits and academic diligence, time management, and financial planning and budgeting. In Category 1, Study Habits and Academic Diligence, students from economically disadvantaged backgrounds exhibited various study habits and a solid commitment to academic excellence. They engaged in a self-directed learning, using every resource available to enhanced their understanding of academic material.

As emphasized by Participant 2, Meymey “kapag po nagtuturo na po yung teacher po namin, madalas po akong nag no notes po sa notebook ko. Lalo na po kapag importante po talaga yung subject tsaka po yung pinag aaralan. Kapag naman po hindi kopo na-notes, nanghihiram po ako ng lecture po ng kaklase ko, L43-L46. Another, Participant 9, Justine, “Para sa pag unlad ng aking pag aaral nakikinig ako sa aking guro at nag lalaan ako ng oras para mag basa” L15-L16, meanwhile, Participant 10, Angela, added that “Ang magandang magagawa ko dito ay nagbabasa ako at nag search minsan sa internet para magkaroon ng kaalaman sa lesson na hindi ko alam” L44-L45.

There was a study that stated tactive engagement in class activities, positive perceptions of educators and the educational environment, strong social connections, and disciplined behavior are key contributors to students' academic achievement.(Özden and Atasoy (2020), Through consistent review and practice, they strive to master complex subjects and improve their academic performance.

As stated by Participant 5 Ysabelle, “Kapag Po uwi ko sa bahay ay pinagaaralan ko po ulit yung mga pinagaralan sa school para Po pag nag quiz or nag recitation ay handa Po ako.” L17, L18,.

Despite numerous challenges, these students remain determined to excel academically, often citing their dreams and aspirations as motivating factors.

In Category 2, Time management have proven as an essential coping strategy for economically disadvantaged students. These students allocated their limited time wisely by creating schedules and routines to efficiently organize their academic tasks and household responsibilities.

As being said by Participant 7, Nathan, “pinagkakasya ko po yung oras ko sa pagrereview at sa mga kailangan ko pong gawin sa bahay.” L12-L13 in addition, said “Nag lalaan po ako ng oras sa pag aaral kasi po minsan hindi ko po talaga matuon ang oras ko sa pag aaral kasi po may mga ginagawa rin po ako sa bahay, gaya nga po ng sabi ko kanina obligasyon ko po talagang gumalaw sa bahay, ginagawa ko na lang po pag may free time ako dun po ako nag aaral yung mga tinuro po ng teachers inaaral ko po ulit para mas matutunan ko po talaga”L31-L35 . Participant 2, to add more, Meymey “Tsaka po nagtatakda din po ako ng mga schedule nang mga gagawin ko” L22.

Moreover, some have mentioned that sacrificing breaks or recreational activities to allocate more time for studying.

Participant 10, Angela, “Kapag may vacant time o kaya nasa bahay ako ginagawa ko ito kapag araw ng sabado at linggo.” L18-L19.

For Category 3, economically disadvantaged students often face financial limitations and must be strategic regarding budgeting and financial planning to stretch their resources. Students described various strategies, such as carefully allocating their funds towards essential school expenses such as transportation, meals, and educational materials

As stated by Participant 1, Allen, “Nagagawa Kong makipag sabayan dahil tinitipid ko Ang baon ko” L14 he added that “Ang pag tulong ko saking magulang na mag tanda. Dahil dito kahit papano ay nagkakaroon ako Ng sapat na Pera para sa aking pagpasok” L59-L60.

Also participants bring packed meals from home or avoid snacking to conserve resources to minimize their expenses.

Participant 4, Arkin, “Nag babaon nalang ako ng kanin at ulam na natitira sa bahay para makapasok ako nang may kinakain sa school” L27-L28, furthermore, Participant 7, Nathan, “Tinitipid ko po yung baon ko para kung walang maibigay sa akin ay makakapasok pa rin ako dahil may ipon ako.” L7-L8 and Participant 10 Angela, “Nasasabayan ko ito sa pamamagitan ng pagtitipid ko sa aking baon, hindi ako nagrecess sa umaga para may pamasaha ako pauwi,at may pang lunch ako sa umaga naman ay inihahatid ako ng aking service”L12-L14.

These students aimed to minimize financial stress through prudent financial management to ensure academic success. Students employed diverse coping mechanisms, including adopting varied learning methodologies, taking responsibility for their academic progress, articulating thoughts effectively, and nurturing self-confidence in their abilities. Additionally, Education GPS (2023) emphasized that poor performance in school doesn't necessarily result from socioeconomic disparities; countries can develop inclusive education systems that mitigate the influence of students' economic backgrounds on their academic performance and outcomes. Conversely, Cockerill et al. (2021) asserted that socioeconomically disadvantaged students exhibit inferior academic achievements compared to their counterparts worldwide.

It is revealed during the observation of the researcher that despite the fact that the participants were burdened with a lot of responsibilities at home, they still managed their time well to continue their studies. The documentation also proved that participants even did their chores at home but still managed their time well to have some space to re-read and revisit lessons. (See appendix E for documentation)

Theme 3: Influence of Support Systems on Resilience

Research reveals that robust support systems comprising family, peers, educators, and community resources significantly contribute to students' ability to navigate socioeconomic challenges and continue their academic pursuits. Positive relationships, mentorship, financial help, and tailored academic support initiatives have been identified as critical factors in enhancing students' resilience and mitigating the adverse effects of socioeconomic challenges on their educational outcomes. Collaboration among stakeholders is crucial in creating supportive, resilient, and equitable student environments.

This theme generates three categories: family support, teacher mentorship and guidance, and peer network support. In Category 1, Family support, the responses emphasized the significant role of family support in the resilience of economically disadvantaged students. Parents have been instrumental in nurturing their children's academic aspirations, providing emotional support, guidance, and practical assistance.

As stated by Participant 1, Allen, “Ang aking ina siya ay tumutulong sakín para makapag patuloy sa pag aaral kahit mahirap Ang buhay nagtutulungan kami para sa pangarap.” L86-L87, to add more, Participant 5, Ysabelle, “Lagi Po nilang sinasabi na kaya ko ito at tuparin ko ang aking mga pangarap sa buhay para mapuntahan ko ang pangarap Kong Lugar na puntahan” L59-L60.

In line with this, a study emphasized that establishing supportive and meaningful connections with educators, counselors, and school personnel can help build the self-confidence of economically disadvantaged students and significantly contribute to their academic achievements (Joseph et al., 2015). The students have expressed gratitude towards their parents, especially for their financial support, which has enabled them to continue their education.

Participant 7, Nathan, “Binibigyan po akong baon at yung mga motivation din po na binibigay nila, gusto ko po na ialis sila sa hirap ng buhay kaya mag-aaral po akong mabuti” L62-L63

Participant 10, Angela, added that “Ang aking mga magulang nakakatulong sila saakin dahil sila ang dahilan kung bakit ako nanatili sa aking pag aaral na kahit ako ay nahihirapan nandyan sila at laging nakasuporta kaya gusto kong makatapos ay para sa magandang kinabukasan ng aking pamilya at sila ay maiahon ko sa kahirapan.” L69-L72, in addition Participant 9, Justine, stated that “Ang aking magulang, lagi silang naka-aalalay at naka suporta sa aking pag aaral.” L45 “nasa tabi ko man sila o wala palagi pa rin silang naka suporta sa aking pag aaral at pangarap” L56-L57, in addition Participant 6, Ivan, “Ang aking magulang, sila ang palaging nandiyan na nagbibigay sa akin ng suporta at sila ang aking inspirasyon upang magpatuloy sa aking pag aaral.” L106- L107.

This support has also motivated and inspired the students to persevere through challenges. Teacher mentorship and guidance also emerge as crucial factors in the academic journey of economically disadvantaged students.

In Category 2, Teacher Mentorship and Guidance, it was seen that teachers have created a nurturing learning environment where students feel valued, supported, and empowered to succeed.

Participant 1, Allen, “handang silang gabayan at tulongan kami sa abot Ng kanilang makakaya” L92 “ he added that Pag suporta at pag gabay samin kung gaano kahalaga ang edukasyon.” L94 then , Participant 2, Meymey, added that “Kaya po natutuwa po ako, nagagalak po ako na nakakatulong po sila para lumakas po yung loob ko na ipagpatuloy yung pag aaral ko po” .L141-L142, also, Participant 3, Via, mentioned that “Nag aano rin po sila nagbibigay po sila ng payo sakin na pagbutihan niyo sa pag aaral para hindi kayo maging mahirap pag tanda” L92-L93 .

The student participant also appreciated their teachers who provided extra help, accommodate their circumstances, and offered encouragements. Also, a study underscores the importance of societal, familial, and school support for students facing economic challenges (Li & Li, 2024). They assert that fostering positive familial bonds and creating a supportive home environment can motivate young individuals to demonstrate resilience. Additionally, some students mention the efforts of teachers to checked on their well-being even outside the classroom, showing a holistic approach to support.

As mentioned by Participant 7, Nathan, “Lagi niya pong pinapalakas loob ko at matiyaga po siya nagtuturo sa mga lessons na hirap po ako at hinahayaan niya po ako magpasa ng late kung ala po akong pera para gawin ang project.” L54-L57.

Participant 6, Ivan, “sila ang nagpapayo at nagsasabi sa amin na dapat kami ay magpatuloy at tuparin ang aming mga pangarap” L59-L60.

Students acknowledged the importance of understanding and supportive teachers who went beyond their roles to assist them in various ways. They showed appreciation to teachers who provided extra help, accommodate their circumstances, and offered encouragement. It was also evident to the responses of the participants during the interview

Participant 2, Meymey, “Tuwing ilang linggo akong hindi nakakapasok ay sila na mismo ang nagpupunta sa aming bahay upang kamustahin ang aking lagay, ako'y lubos na nagagalak sapagkat nakakatulong ito upang lumakas ang loob ko na ipagpatuloy ang aking pag aaral.”, L138-L140, in addition, Participant 5, Ysabelle, “yung mga teacher namin kapag Po Hindi kami pumapasok ng ilang Araw or buwan binibisita Po nila kami sa bahay-bahay namin para alamin ang lagay namin.” L-44-L45.

Lastly under this theme, Category 3, Peer Support Networks, economically disadvantaged students often depended on their peers for assistance and support, significantly impacting their resilience. Students mentioned that they rely on classmates and friends for academic help, such as sharing notes, explaining concepts, or assisting with assignments.

Participant 3, Via, stated that “Nakakatulong po sila kasi po kagaya nga po ng sinabi ko minsan po absent ako sila po yung nagsasabi sakin na may gagawin ganon po sila kaya po nakakatulong sila sakin, saka sila rin po yung nagsasabi na maki hotspot ako sa kanila pag nandito po sa school eto yung isearch ganon po”. L39-L42, so in addition Participant 5, Ysabelle, “kapag Po nahihirapan ako sa mga activities sa kanila Po ako nagtatanong kumbaga Po tulong tulong Po kami para Maka graduate kami at para Po Walang maiwan.” L23-L25, then Participant 7, Nathan, also stated that “kapag absent po ako sila po nagsasabi sa akin ng mga ginawa tapos binibigyan din nila ako ng miryenda minsan kaya nakakatipid po ako” L20-L22..

Furthermore, peer support goes beyond academics, with friends offering emotional support, encouragement, advice, and understanding during challenging times. They also lend their economically disadvantaged classmates money when needed .

Participant 1 Allen, stated “Oo lubhang nakaka tulong sila Hindi man pinansyal pero tumutulong sila sa pamamagitan Ng pag suporta para mas Lalo ko pang galingan sa pag aaral kasi gusto ko din pong masabayan ung mga kaibigan ko” L40-L41.

A study aslo stated that constructive and positive relationships with teachers and peers can strengthen children's resilience (Morrison & Allen, 2007). This sense of solidarity fosters a supportive learning environment where students feel valued and motivated despite challenges.

As observed by the researcher, having positive relationships, mentorship, financial help, tailored academic support initiatives have been identified as critical factors in enhancing students' resilience and mitigating the adverse effects of socioeconomic challenges on

their educational outcomes. And lastly, student participants get along well with their peers and teacher, as documented, they spent time with their friends that they considered as one of their major support systems (see appendix E).

Theme 4: Resourcefulness of Students

In times of adversity, the human spirit often shows its remarkable capacity for resourcefulness. Economically disadvantaged students demonstrate an inspiring resilience, utilizing every opportunity and exploring avenues to overcome challenges and pursue their educational goals. Through their actions, they show their determination and resourcefulness in the face of hardship.

Two categories have emerged from this theme which includes utilizing available resources and seeking alternative solutions. For Category 1, in Utilizing Available Resources, economically disadvantaged students often exhibit resourcefulness in utilizing available resources to support their learning. Despite financial constraints, they strive to maximize what they have.

As stated by Participant 2, Meymey, “tuwing may load ang kaibigan ko ay nakikikonek ako upang maka download ng mga video tungkol sa pinag aaralan namin. Dahil dito ay mas natututo ako. Madalas din ay nagbabasa ako ng libro na galing sa iskwelahan.” L12, L13, L14, another response, Participant 5 Arkin, “Nag babaon nalang ako ng kanin at ulam na natitira sa bahay para makapasok ako nang may kinakain sa school” L4, L5, in addition, Participant 10, Angela, “hindi ako nagrecess sa umaga para may pamasaha ako pauwi, at may pang lunch ako sa umaga naman ay inihahatid ako ng aking service.” L5, L6, L7.

Access to resources significantly impacts students, particularly those who were disadvantaged or marginalized (Valant et al., 2022). Also, a study revealed that any disadvantaged households lack access to educational materials like books and toys, which were essential for laying the foundation for learning (Blazer, 2009). These actions demonstrated their resilience in making the most out of what was available to them, highlighting their determination to succeed despite the challenges they faced. In addition to utilizing available resources, economically disadvantaged students display a knack for seeking alternative solutions to overcome obstacles.

In Category 2, Seeking Alternative Solutions is evident as stated by

Participant 2, Meymey, “Tuwing wala akong masakyan ay naglalakad na lamang ako kahit mahuli sa klase.” L32, L33, another response, Participant 1, Allen, “Ang pag tulong ko saking magulang na mag tanda. Dahil dito kahit papano ay nagkakaroon ako Ng sapat na Pera para sa aking pagpasok Hindi Rin Naman Kasi sakín mahalaga Ang maraming baon Ang mahalaga sakín ay maka pasok ako at matuto.” L20, L21, L22, L23.

Research shows that resourcefulness is a valuable trait not only for children from economically disadvantaged backgrounds but also for families striving to achieve their life goals with limited resources (Li et al., 2018). These actions reflect their proactive approach to problem-solving and their willingness to explore different avenues to ensure their academic progress. However, qualitative research reveals that students from lower economic backgrounds exhibit resourcefulness, displaying resilience, creativity, and determination in finding alternative learning opportunities (Fauzan & Zuraida, 2023).

The primary benefit of resourcefulness for children was its positive impact on academic performance. Studies indicated that promoting resourcefulness within the school environment leads to faster learning and greater progress compared to peers who do not receive resourcefulness-focused education (Li et al., 2018).

In the study it was revealed that despite not having enough, students participants are observed to be resourceful, asking and seeking help from their peers when there was a need to do assignment using internet connection, they asked for help, another thing is, they made sure that they are saving enough from the allowances that was given to them to make sure that even if they were not given allowance by their parents for school, they can still go to class because they have savings.

Theme 5: Persistence and Determination

Persistence and determination were evident among economically disadvantaged students during their face-to-face learning. Despite facing financial constraints, students demonstrated resilience in pursuing their education and remained committed to education, refusing to be deterred by setbacks or obstacles. Education became a hope for these students and a path to breaking the cycle of poverty. Additionally, students emphasized the importance of maintaining a positive mindset and remaining dedicated to their goals, which are crucial in overcoming obstacles. For these students, it is not simply a matter of attending classes but also of demonstrating persistence and determination in their studies.

Three categories emerged from this theme including self-motivation, positive thinking, and pursuing dreams. In Category 1, Self Motivation, economically disadvantaged students often rely on self-motivation to persevere in their studies. It can be seen in the responses of the participants.

Participant 1, Allen, “Oo maman dahil kapag mas tinututukan ko ang pag aaral tiyak na makaka kuha ako ng malaking marka o grado para sakín napaka halaga ng mataas na grado dahil ito ang basehan ng mga tao para maka kuha ng maganda at maayos na trabaho.” L10, L11, L12, in addition, Participant 8, Althea “Pumapasok pa rin ako na kahit alam ko sa sarili ko na hindi ako yung estudyanteng masipag mag aral at sobrang talino pero gagawin ko pa rin ang aking makakaya para tumaas ang grades at maka graduate.” L32, L33, L34, another response from Participant 10 Angela, “Ang tumutulong sa akin na magpatuloy sa pag aaral ay ang aking sariling

kagustuhang makatapos at makatulong sa aking pamilya.” L29, L30.

It was revealed in a study that the concept of learning motivation among disadvantaged students suggested that their motivation to learn, often lower than that of students from more privileged backgrounds, significantly contributes to their educational struggles, (Fejes, 2012). Also, even facing financial hardships and other challenges, they remain driven by their desire to succeed and achieve their goals. But, despite this, there is a lack of research examining the psychological traits or learning motivations of economically disadvantaged students (Chen et al., 2009; Hummel & Randler, 2012).

In Category 2, Positive Thinking, maintaining a positive mindset was another key factor that contributed to the resilience of economically disadvantaged students. Despite facing numerous challenges, they choose to see the silver lining and remained hopeful about their future. These students mentioned staying optimistic on their studies, as stated by

Participant 4 Arkin, “Pagiging positibo at determinado, kaya kahit na may pagsubok o kahirapan, patuloy akong nag titiyaga at nagpursigi upang makamit ang aking mga layunin.” L23, L24, another response, Participant 5 Ysabelle, “Always positive Po at wag isipin ang mga negatibong bagay.” L19, in addition, Ivan, “Isa lang na pamamaraan ang aking ginagawa ito ay ang pagpapanatili ko ng positibong pag iisip dahil minsan sa mga oras na nakakaranas ako ng stress o pagkabigo ay pinipilit ko pa rin manatiling positibo at tumingin sa aking mga pangarap.” L20, L21, L22, L23, moreover, Participant 9 Justine, “ginagawa ko lang laging positibo ang aking isip.” L17, Participant 8 Althea, “its ok to go to school from having nothing except you are at home but doing nothing.” L5, L6.

In addition, Cole et al. (2004) added that positive thinking propose that learning motivation, was one of the key predictor of academic success, activates certain psychological factors in economically disadvantaged students and influences their academic performance (Li et al., 2020). By adopting a positive outlook, they are better equipped to handle setbacks and persevere through difficult times, ultimately fueling their determination to succeed.

For Category 3, Pursuing Dreams, economically disadvantaged students often draw inspiration from their dreams and aspirations, used them as powerful motivators to persevere in their studies. Whether it's aspiring for a better future for themselves or wanting to support their families, their dreams served as a driving forces that propel them forward. As stated by

Participant 5 Ysabelle, “Pumapasok Po ako kahit Walang baon kasi Po Hindi Po hadlang ang kahirapan para matupad ang ating mga pangarap sa buhay.” L15, L6, Participant 2 Meymey, “kahit ako ay estudyanteng may kakulangang pinansyal ay nakakayanan kong magpatuloy pa rin sa pag aaral. Dahil alam kong kahit imposible ay nagagawa kong posible dahil nakakahanap ako ng mga paraan upang makapag aral.” L21, L22, L23, she also added “Na ako ay nagsisikap upang makapag aral, upang matuto, at upang makapagtapos. “ L43, L44, in addition Participant 9, Justine, “pag may pangarap ka maliit man o malaki ang ibigay sayo patuloy ka pa rin sa pag aaral.” L7, L8, and Participant 10 Angela, “ginaganahan ako na mas lalong pagpursigihan ang aking pag aaral” L13.

In addition, young people facing adversities in their lives, for whom school may served as the only refuge, stability, and welcoming environment, are the ones who could benefit the most from positive education (Roffey & Quinlan, 2021).

It was also observed in the study that the student participants were determined to continue to school despite their circumstances. As seen during the documentation of the researcher, the students can really walk a long mile just to be able to attend school on time, even if they have to leave home too early, and got home in the afternoon and it was already late. Walking also without any shed was very simple for them, they didn't mind it, their only goal was to attend school and continue to learn (see appendix E for documentation).

Structural Description

According to Moustakas (1994), structural descriptions are used to write a description of the context or setting that influences how the participants experience the phenomenon. The experiences of economically disadvantaged students are varied and complicated, influenced by various factors such as time, space, causality, materiality, relationship to others and self, and bodily factors, all of which affect their resilience.

Time

Moustakas 1994, stated that time is a description of a person's experiences on a certain phenomenon in relation to time. In this research, the structural description focused on how the student participants experienced that time was one of the their enemies, since they are still in a very young age, they have are already experiencing the difficulties of life as economically disadvantaged students, coming to school without any allowances, just with packed lunch from home that was reserved from last nights meal, a participant stated that “There was a time na pumasok ako without having something to eat or money to buy some foods pero hindi yon nagging epekto para hindi ako pumasok”.

Space

This is the descriptions of a person's lived-experiences that involves the situations when they faced or experienced the phenomena. (Moustakas, 1994). These students face challenges in their physical and social environments due to limited finances and resources. As a result, they often feel being left behind. However, they show resilience by creating spaces of hope and possibility within their constraints, and a participant said that “Hindi agad ako sumusuko sa pag-aaral kahit mahirap at maraming problema, dahil wala namang

problema na hindi nasosolusyunan”. A factor that also contributes to the resiliency of the students was finding a space within the circle of friends that influenced them to be resilient. An example of this was the statement of one of the participants, Nakakatulong po sila kasi po kagaya nga po ng sinabi ko minsan po absent ako sila po yung nagsasabi sakín na may gagawin ganon po sila kaya po nakakatulong sila sakín, saka sila rin po yung nagsasabi na maki hotspot ako sa kanila pag nandito po sa school eto yung isearch ganon po”.

Casuality

It is the description of how certain factors have influenced a person’s live experiences on the phenomenon. (Moustakas, 1994). In terms of casuality, many people face inequality and unfairness due to their background and economic circumstances like what the student participants are experiencing, but despite that a participant stated that “nakakapagod at stress pero sulit naman lahat ng iyon dahil natututo din naman ako kahit papaano.”. However, they are determined to overcome these obstacles and create a better future for themselves, a participant said that “kahit ako ay estudyanteng may kakulangang pinansyal ay nakakayanan kong magpatuloy pa rin sa pag aaral. Dahil alam kong kahit imposible ay nagagawa kong posible dahil nakakahanap ako ng mga paraan upang makapag aral.” Despite, economic hardships, determination and persistence can lead to success.

Materiality

When it comes to materiality, it is the descriptions of how the lived experiences of a person are affected by materiality or the reality of the world (Moustakas, 1994). In the study, students participants living conditions greatly affect their lives, as they struggle with limited resources and everyday challenges like finding getting enough food. Despite these difficulties, they often find ways to adapt and make the best of what they have. Participants are experiencing financial difficulties as stated during the interview, “Mahirap po minsan lalo kapag wala po kaming naibabaon” “Sobrang hirap po talaga mag-aral kapag walang pangkain at pamasaha” “Minsan mahirap dahil sa kakulangan sa budget kapag may kailangan gastusin sa paaralan” And with a lot of material thing that they lacked, they still managed to be resourceful and utilized only the available materials that they have, especially when there are projects and activities that are required to do. “hindi ako nagrecess sa umaga para may pamasaha ako pauwi, at may pang lunch ako sa umaga naman ay inihatid ako ng aking service.” tuwing may load ang kaibigan ko ay nakikikonek ako upang maka download ng mga video tungkol sa pinag aaralan namin. Dahil dito ay mas natututo ako. Madalas din ay nagbabasa ako ng libro na galing sa iskwelahan.”. It shows their resiliency through resourcefulness.

Bodily Concerns

It is the descriptions of a person’s lived experiences which involves his/her body reactions such as emotions, etc. on the phenomenon. (Moustakas, 1994). Students from low-income backgrounds face both challenges and support in their relationships. They rely on their families and communities for help, but also experience feelings of isolation and shame due to poverty. “Pumapasok pa rin ako na kahit alam ko sa sarili ko na hindi ako yung estudyanteng masipag mag aral at sobrang talino pero gagawin ko pa rin ang aking makakaya para tumaaas ang grades at maka graduate.” Despite these obstacles, they find ways to connect with others and stay strong against social exclusion, and they have good relationship to others, like what a participants mentioned “kapag absent po ako sila po nagsasabi sa akin ng mga ginawa tapos binibigyan din nila ako ng miryenda minsan kaya nakakatipid po ako” People who are struggling with economic hardships often face physical challenges, evident in a response of a participant stated that “Tuwing wala akong masakyan ay naglalakad na lamang ako kahit mahuli sa klase. Despite these difficulties, they show resilience and determination by not letting their physical limitations hold them back from achieving their aspirations.

Relationship to Self and Others

Lastly, it is the descriptions of a person’s lived experiences involving their personal reactions, introspections, and interactions with others as well. (Moustakas, 1994). When it comes to the participants relationship to other and self, it was evident that participants exhibits a good relationship to themselves and other, “minsang ay na stress at nawalan ng motivation” he also added “sa mga oras na nakakaranas ako ng stress o pagkabigo ay pinipilit ko pa rin manatiling positibo at tumingin sa aking mga pangarap.” They are managing stress well despite their socio economic situations.” Nakakastress po minsan pero okay naman at kaya naman”. Though they are exhausted from being at school for the whole day, they still managed to help with the chores at home, doing laundry, washing the dishes, and even taking care of their younger sibling.

Essence

From the structural and textural descriptions, the researcher then writes a composite description that presents the “essence” of the phenomenon, called the essential, invariant structure (or essence). Primarily this passage focuses on the common experiences of the participants (Moustakas, 1994).

One of the specific cases of the participants that showed resiliency was having to walk before sunrise just to arrive at school for her first subject in the morning, and also having to walk again after school from 4:30 in the afternoon and arriving at home after an hour before the sun sets in the evening. And there are also participants who are coming to school without any money or allowance to spend, just a simple leftover meal from home. In addition to their socioeconomic problems, which had something to do with finances, most of them are also struggling with frequent absences that affect their learning. However, the support system was one way for the

economically disadvantaged students to be resilient if face-to-face learning. Support from parents, teachers and peers motivated them to continue, despite challenges.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Socioeconomic status significantly impacts economically disadvantaged students' educational experiences, leading to financial constraints affecting learning experiences, difficulty balancing academic and personal responsibilities, and stress. Economically disadvantaged students employ various strategies to improve their academic achievement, including managing allowances, prioritizing essential expenses, and using available resources so that they can attend school every day. They also seek peer assistance and maintain a positive attitude.

Classmates and friends play significant roles in supporting economically disadvantaged students academically and emotionally, providing encouragement, sharing study materials, and offering financial assistance. To overcome academic challenges, students use coping strategies including study habits, time management, financial planning, persistence, and determination.

Support systems including family, teachers, and peers significantly contribute to students' resilience and academic success, providing emotional, academic, and financial support. Despite facing socio economic challenges, economically disadvantaged students demonstrate resilience and determination, prioritizing education and working towards achieving academic goals.

This qualitative study provided a descriptive understanding of economically disadvantaged students' lived experiences and resiliency during face-to-face learning, suggests that:

For students, they should continue their education despite their socioeconomic circumstances. These circumstances may hinder them in many ways, but perseverance, determination, and resilience will pay off in the long run and lead to better opportunities.

For Parents. The study suggests to continue guiding the student participants in their learning journey, helping them to foster growth and will help them overcome the adversities in learning. Also, strengthen your relationship with your children because your parents are their backbone.

For Social Studies Teachers, the study suggests the need for teacher training in supporting economically disadvantaged students. Investigating the impact of various training models and ongoing professional development could reveal how educators can be equipped to foster inclusive classrooms and meet these students' specific needs. Also, integrate in the different lessons in Araling Panlipunan different ways on how students can develop resiliency.

School Heads create strategically organized plans and programs aimed at addressing the specific challenges and concerns related to resilience among economically disadvantaged students, thereby fostering an environment conducive to their academic success and overall well-being.

For Guidance Counselors, they can craft a targeted interventions and support programs specifically for the need of the students with unique circumstances and learning requirements of economically challenged students, thereby empowering them to navigate obstacles and sustain their educational journey with confidence and resilience

For the Department of Education, this study focused on face-to-face learning. Considering the increasing adoption of online learning, it would be beneficial to investigate how economically disadvantaged students navigate online learning environments, their challenges, and the support systems needed to ensure success in these settings.

For Further researchers in this area could focus on comparing the experiences of economically disadvantaged students in different geographic locations or grade levels to understand how various factors influence their educational experiences and outcomes. Additionally, further research could explore practical strategies for engaging families from low socioeconomic backgrounds in their children's education. This could include identifying the barriers to parental involvement and developing strategies to increase parental engagement in their children's education.

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